

How to cite: Škutor, M., & Đerek, M. (2024). With Nature in Nature -Teaching in Nature. *World conference on future innovations and sustainable solutions*. Futurity Research Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14012064>

With Nature in Nature -Teaching in Nature

Marijana Škutor¹, Mirjana Đerek²

¹doc.dr.sc., University of Slavonski Brod, Croatia

² Classroom teacher, Primary school Franica Dall" era Vir, Posušje, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Accepted: October 13, 2024 | **Published:** October 30, 2024 | **Language:** English

Abstract: Teaching in nature is a creative teaching method and an innovative way of teaching. It is assumed that students in nature are more motivated and have a better aspiration of teaching content exposed in nature. The aim of this paper is to point out the importance of being in nature with students and teaching teaching content in the natural environment. In this way, an excellent correlation with all subjects is achieved, and through this project the students became more aware of the importance of preserving nature with the goal of a healthier and better quality of life.

Keywords: connection between nature and students, collaborative relationships, environmental protection, innovative approach to teaching, stay in nature.

Introduction

After many years of experience and working with children, the authors saw the students' interest and desire for innovative teaching in nature. Based on this, significant dates are planned starting in the spring of 2022, which will be marked and taught in nature. The marked dates are: First Day of Spring, Forest Day, Water Day, World Health Day, Easter, Planet Earth Day, School Day and First Day of Autumn so that students can compare and record significant changes in nature. An innovative approach to teaching is a challenge and a pleasure for students and teachers because it opens up a new and different perspective for learning and adopting new teaching content. Knowledge is transferred to students in a completely new way through concrete and vivid examples.

New teaching contents were learned outside the classroom, so the excitement and curiosity of the students was obvious. Through the project *With nature into nature*, an excellent correlation was achieved with all subjects (Croatian language, art, music, TK and mathematics). Students were provided with a modern approach to learning content, and outside the classroom, in a relaxed atmosphere, students acquired new knowledge much more easily, exchanged their experiences and previous knowledge about the environment. Better communication among students was noticed, which significantly influenced the quality of collaborative relationships. Man inevitably affects nature and it affects him, so it is important to respect each other, and that already in the early years, the family and school promote the importance of nature conservation through lectures on environmental topics. Salazar et al. 2020 believe that through connection with nature, man identifies with the natural landscape and creates its relationship to the elements of the landscape. Schultz (2002), emphasizes the concept of inclusion with nature through three key components, namely: connection with nature, care for nature and commitment to nature protection, but two components are enough to achieve harmony with nature and be an advocate of environmental preservation. The tendency to preserve the environment in children develops already in preschool age in the family and in schools, and the key role is played by parents and teachers who possess competencies that promote the care of nature and its protection. In the family, the importance of the well-being of nature and its preservation should be emphasized, as well as the insistence on children's and parents' stay in nature as often as possible. Point out the importance of clean air, water, the preservation of plant and animal life, as well as the proper disposal of waste. Connection with nature is correlated with connection between people and building quality relationships. Self-perception of the importance of nature conservation and acceptance of the value system is the primary goal in environmental protection and responsible behavior in nature. (Lee et al., 2015). Sever et al. 2017, emphasize the importance of teaching students in nature and its benefits for all children's developmental areas. These authors believe that the aspiration of students is higher when teaching in nature, because the students are more relaxed and through nature lessons in nature, they better understand and adopt the teaching content. When spending time in nature, children activate all their senses, take the initiative and undertake actions that they would not dare to do in class, strengthen their skills and develop new abilities. Sobko (2019) believes that the benefits of nature are essential for growth and development, because children spend more and more time indoors. The benefits of being in nature for children's physical and mental health are indisputable. Wells and Evans (2003, according to Yu, 2012)

Research Results

Extracurricular teaching is a part of the educational process that has great cognitive and methodical significance because students find the best ways and means of learning through research in nature. Quality teacher preparation is a prerequisite for the success of teaching in nature with the aim of actively acquiring as much content as possible from nature and society, through research work in extracurricular teaching. The program of the school in nature is divided into 3 basic parts: educational, sports-recreational and cultural-entertaining. The educational part is realized from the beginning of the arrangement and preparation for the school in nature, and ends after the return, that is, during the analysis of the school in nature. The sports-recreational part in nature and the cultural-entertainment part are organized with different themes that encourage children's creativity and

independence. It includes the contents of TK, as well as art and music classes from regular classes held at the destination school in nature. Since there are meadows, forests and hills in the immediate vicinity of the school, it was decided that from the beginning of spring 2022, most of the nature and social classes will be held in nature. The goal was to achieve correlation with other subjects to fully implement the curriculum. The parents of our students also helped us in the research. Pupils' artistic and written works with appropriate photographs were placed on a poster, and part of it was used to create a picture book. Spring of 2022. The work continued in the next school year by filling in the posters, and after the end of the fall, the Autumn 2022 picture book was created. Each season has its own charms and challenges, it is up to us to discover, recognize, explore and love them through being in nature and observing it. Lifelong values are learned together through cooperation between teacher-student-parents and educational goals are realized, with the dawning of new ones. knowledge and skills, strengthening of personality as well as raising awareness of nature conservation, development of society and love for our homeland Bosnia and Herzegovina. The goals of the work: 1) to develop love for nature; 2) develop a positive attitude towards walking and being in nature; 3) arouse interest in research and life in harmony with nature; 4) Realize that man is a part of nature; 5) Take care of health; 6) Get to know the characteristics of individual seasons. Outcomes of the work: To develop an interest in learning about the laws of nature. Systematically influence the development of all psychological abilities, influence the development of certain abilities, primarily observation, description, conclusion, comparison. To develop an interest in learning about the laws of nature. Systematically influence the development of all psychic abilities, influence the development of certain abilities, primarily observation, description, conclusion, comparison, etc. [Detailed description of activities in nature](#) - The first day of spring, Forest Day, is celebrated on March 21, 2022. The students and the teacher stayed in nature to welcome spring. While walking in the forest, they sang songs about spring, observed the first signs and symbols of spring. Passing through the forest path, we talked about the importance of forests, their preservation and the richness of the forest cover of our homeland. Students presented their impressions, observations and conclusions about the weather in spring. After returning to the classroom, the students described their experiences from nature orally and in writing, and the students' works were placed on a poster. On World Water Day, March 22, 2022. year, a walk was made to the river Ričina, to point out the importance of water conservation. Birds chirped along the way, and yellow primroses, the harbingers of spring, were everywhere in the meadow. After observing the river course, the terms riverbed, left and right bank, source and mouth were repeated. Flora and fauna in and around the river were observed. A section along the riverbed where plastic bottles and cans were thrown was cleaned, and the students again pointed out the importance of preserving clean water because it is the source of life. Cheerful and joyful students sang a spring song by the river, and after that they returned to their classroom. Full of impressions in the art class, they expressed part of what they saw with drawings. They also created a Water Day poster with messages about the importance of water. On March 24, 2022, a nature and society research class were held. Since in research teaching the primary place is occupied by awareness, which we achieve by observing nature and natural phenomena, the students were given tasks that will enable them to study and connect phenomena and processes within nature and society: plants, animals and time. After arriving at their destination (at the foot of Mount Čubrina), the students set to work diligently and diligently. They recorded their observations on a sheet of paper, expressed their impressions and

concluded that this nature lesson was educational and fun. With this nature lesson, we achieved a correlation with other subjects: Croatian language: Villa Spring art culture (harbingers of spring, musical culture spring song, mathematics (word tasks), physical and health culture (running, natural forms of movement). March 28, 2022. Nature is rich in various medicinal plants. On the weekend they went for a walk and picked violets, which we brought to school. The process of preparing the violet syrup took place the next day. The next day, sugar was added to the liquid. The syrup was mixed over a low heat and poured into bottles with labels on the product, which the students took home on April 7, 2022, with the aim of raising awareness about health. After picking 400 dandelions, the students and the teacher started the process of preparing dandelion honey. The flowers are washed, boiled in water and sugar with pieces of lemon. At the end, the honey is drained and poured into prepared jars. Students took two jars home each, and the rest were given to dear guests on School Day. April 17, 2022, Easter, Easter, the biggest Christian holiday celebrated in the spring, is celebrated. The students picked sprigs of mica-maca in nature by the river Ričina, which they shaped into wreaths and bunnies during the art class. So, they made Easter decorations and discussed the importance of preserving faith and tradition. April 22, 2022, Earth Day. The importance of preserving planet Earth, the environment, air, water and nature was discussed. So that we can live in harmony with nature and use its benefits. With a small contribution, our faithful students wanted to point out the importance of preserving the environment. They planted a small flower for a happier world. They made a poster with eco messages to the Earth. 01.06.2022 School Day, this day was celebrated in the schoolyard in a natural environment. Dear guests were given a jar of honey that was made at the school. The story of the process of making medicinal honey from dandelions was briefly presented, and the guests were delighted with a little magic, work and effort. At the parents' meeting at the end of the school year, the project and the results so far were briefly presented to the parents, and they expressed their enthusiasm. They confirmed that they, too, independently made dandelion honey at home. The children were proud because they were the ones in charge of the preparation. Flipping through the photos and children's works in the order in which they happened, they were connected and bound in a picture book, and the same testified to the student's Project in nature. On the school day, dear guests: principals, government representatives, retired employees were given a jar of honey. Delighted with the work and effort of the students, a one-day trip to the Livno dairy was organized at the suggestion of the principal. We also received an award for the work My Healthy Habits, a story in which a student described the habit of using honey in everyday life.

Conclusions

With this small project, the students contributed to the awareness of students, teachers, parents and the local community about the importance of preserving nature from pollution and pointed out the benefits that nature provides us. The importance of teaching in nature as an innovative method that correlates with increased student interest and easier acquisition of teaching content was also highlighted. Students, teachers and parents recognized the value of the project, showed interest in research, and even made medicinal honey at home. Preservation of flora and fauna should be imperative in educational institutions. Involving parents and the local community in school nature conservation projects with the aim of strengthening partnerships and preserving health is one of the ways to preserve the nature that we have only borrowed from future generations. The students sent a

message about the importance of being in nature, in the fresh air, through various forms of recreation, exercise or just being in the fresh air.

References

- Andić, D., Papak, P. P., & Mezak, J. (2020). How to foster a significant connectedness with nature in children through the quality organization of children's leisure time and the use of ICT in school? In Proceedings of EDULEARN20 Conference (Vol. 6, 7th ed.). Retrieved February 20, 2023, from <https://library.iated.org/publications/EDULEARN>
- Estok, S. (2018). *The ecophobia hypothesis*. New York, NY, and London, UK: Routledge. ISBN 978-1-351-38493-3.
- Lee, K., Ashton, M. C., Choi, J., & Zachariassen, K. (2015). Connectedness to nature and to humanity: Their association and personality correlates. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6, 1003. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.01003>
- Pecko, L. (2019). Cooperative learning in primary education teaching. *Methodological Horizons*, 14(1(26)), 73-94. <https://doi.org/10.32728/mo.14.1.2019.05>
- Salazar, G., Kunkle, K., & Monroe, M. C. (2020). *Practitioner guide to assessing connection to nature*. Washington, DC: NAAEE. Retrieved May 25, 2023, from <https://naaee.org/eepro/publication/practitioner-guide-assessing-connection>
- Schultz, P. W. (2002). Inclusion with Nature: The Psychology of Human-Nature Relations. In *Psychology of Sustainable Development* (pp. 61-78). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-0995-0>
- Sever, I., Vranić, M., Bošnjak, K., Čačić, I., Protulipac, M., & Klepac, M. (2017). Assessments of teachers and students about extracurricular teaching in nature in elementary schools in the City of Zagreb. *Metodički Ogledi*, 24(1), 95-108. <https://doi.org/10.21464/mo45.124.95108>
- Sobko, T., Jia, Z., & Brown, G. (2018). Measuring connectedness to nature in preschool children in an urban setting and its relation to psychological functioning. *PLOS ONE*, 13(11), e0207057. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0207057>
- Vukelić, N. (2020). Determinants of (future) teachers' readiness for education for sustainable development. *Napredak*, 161(1-2), 141-161. Retrieved March 15, 2023, from <https://hrcak.srce.hr/239898>
- Wainwright, N. (2021). The foundation phase in Wales, outdoor learning, and motor development. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 21, 567-573. Retrieved February 2021, from <https://efsupit.ro/images/stories/februarie2021/Art%2064.pdf>